
APPLICATIONS OF MACHINE LEARNING, KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY AND DATA MINING IN THE ANALYSIS, CLASSIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT OF REMOTELY SENSED GEOSPATIAL SATELLITE DATA

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning, knowledge discovery and data mining techniques are found to be inadequately used in terms of apriori data cleaning when analyzing those aspects of a remote sensing satellite image dataset that can help accurately assess and predict conclusive features and patterns pertaining to land use and land cover analysis. In this project it is proposed to use the various existing tools in the data mining community to extract useful cluster patterns from the data set for easier and precise representation in the form of classified maps. Data cleaning will be explored from a trainable neural network and a supervised – unsupervised learning point of view and useful comparisons will be drawn. This procedure will include elimination of noise and precise labeling of samples under diverse cost and multi-class distributions which are typical of remotely sensed data. Sample selection is based on applying an apriori statistical distance metric with a useful approximation of the threshold value. Data in this project has been randomized and biases eliminated before executing the sample/feature selection routines. In conclusion the final data classification maps/results would be presented and the corresponding statistics analyzed and evaluated. The end results will be compared against the results obtained from the commercial MultiSpec [11] remote sensing software.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Remote sensing has been conceptualized as the science and art of obtaining information about an object, area or phenomenon through the analysis of data acquired by a device that is not in contact with the object, area or phenomenon [8]. The data collected may be spatial, spectral or temporal in nature and the features thus established may be represented in the image space, feature space or the signal space. The objective of remote sensing is to estimate the surface property at an unobserved location from data acquired remotely.

1.1 Problems Associated with RS Data:

Remote sensing data however suffers from severe disturbances due to noise and data irregularities. These are essentially induced due to the earth's curvature being spherical while the flight path and plane of motion assumed regular, ignoring the reflection,

scattering and transmission of signals from other particles in the atmospheres, signal multi-path phenomena, signal interference with land and air based structures, temperature, air electron content and other such parameters. Overlapping of clusters of data is also a well known problem given the similarities in the spectral signatures of various classes in the study area.

1.2 Geospatial Data:

Spatial data is the data related to objects that occupy space. A spatial database stores spatial objects represented by spatial data types and spatial relationships among such objects. Spatial data carries topological and or distance information and it is often organized by spatial indexing structures and accessed by spatial search methods. Some typical examples include: ground based spectrometer data, thermal sensor imagery, LIDAR imagery, RADAR imagery, MS/HS imagery, IR imagery, photogrammetric imagery and GPS data. Traditional (non-spatial) databases are concerned with only the attributes of objects. They make no explicit distinction between the location of an object and its other attributes. A given spatial database provides for the storage and manipulation of four aspects of its data –

- Location component
- Topological component
- Attribute component
- Metadata component

The location component is a record of the position in geographical space that determines where something is and what form it takes. The topological component is a record of the logical relationships between different geographic objects. The attribute component is a record of the characteristics of things that determine what geographic objects represent and what properties they have. The metadata component is a thorough documentation of the contents of the overall database.

1.3 Methods of Organizing Spatial Data:

The organization of data for the purpose of data mining can be done in the following spatial models –

- Stock matrix
- Interaction matrix
- Network
- List
- Raster

In this study, either the *raster* format of the spatial data sets have been extensively used where in the data is stored and manipulated on, as a sequence of pixel values or converted to their corresponding (x,y) *vector* format.

1.4 Spatial Data Formats:

The relational organization (REL) in the raster form is the starting point or the basic organization of remotely sensed data in data mining. Spatial datasets are organized in different formats like:

- band sequential (BSQ)
- band interleaved by line (BIL)
- band interleaved by pixel (BIP)
- bit interleaved by bit (BIB)
- bit sequential (BSQ)

1.5 Why Machine Learning in Remote Sensing Data Analysis?

Spatial data mining methods can be applied to extract interesting patterns, functional sequences, models and regular “knowledge” from large spatial databases. In particular, they can be used for understanding spatial data, discovering relationships between spatial and non-spatial data, construction of spatial knowledge-bases, query optimization, data reorganization in spatial databases, capturing the general characteristics in simple and concise manner, etc. The project is envisaged under the assumption that Data mining techniques help understand and manipulate the four *components* of geo-spatial data enlisted above, the best. A useful comparison can be made here with respect to the applicability of *geographic information systems* (GIS) in this regard but it has been noted that GIS is not as flexible and robust as ML/DM in the component based analysis of geo-spatial data. Data mining in remote sensing has three major components - *Clustering or Classification, Association Rules and Sequence Analysis*. Knowledge discovery in databases (KDD) is one such step towards realizing information as a production factor. The primary tasks of data mining in practice are prediction and description. *Prediction* involves using some variables or fields in the database to predict unknown or future values of other variables of interest. *Description* focuses on finding interpretable patterns that describe the data.

2. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

Simulation of data-sets into visual patterns provides for a better understanding of the data as human perception is enhanced. Through this project it is planned to implement various machine learning and data mining exercises aimed at realizing the extensive satellite image data associated with land use and land cover phenomena into easily interpretable photo realistic images, which can be used for analysis and assessment by land development planners, surveyors, cartographers, agronomists, farmers, soil experts, geographers and other interested audience. Using satellite imagery in combination with GIS and GPS for precision agriculture shows a lot of promise in the

usefulness of these technologies. This project would thus help achieve a better understanding on the applicability of knowledge based learning for optimal classification of huge remote sensing geo-spatial data sets.

3. RELATED WORK:

Amalendu Roy [3] in his research has presented a method of deriving association rules by decision tree induction for the classification of spatial data using Peano Count Tree (PC-Tree). This method is a lossless representation of a bit and of a spatial dataset from which the original data can be completely reconstructed and which contains 1-bit count of each quadrant in the original space. The author claims that this method is far more efficient than the existing techniques given that it performs classification through logical operations aimed at recognizing the relative information gain. In his research, Andrew Kusiak [4] introduces the concept of data farming which deals with the process and the methods used to determine the most appropriate features for data collection and subsequent analysis and classification given partial availability of temporally varying data. The method introduced aims at defining new features for temporal information collection and related spatial data mining. William Perrizo, et al., [5] propose a new method for association rule mining and classification on spatial datasets using P-trees and bit sequential data formats for lossless image compression and representation for applications in precision farming, community planning and resource discovery. They also suggest the use of Markov-process based modeling and grammatical inference techniques for the mining of temporal sequences of data. A case study on RSI data [6] talks about the use of the P-ARM algorithm which is a modified version of the apriori algorithm that accommodates the PC-tree data structure for bit sequential data formats of the spatial imagery. RSI data essential includes thematic data which can be either infrared/thermal or multi-spectral. Naren Ramakrishnan and Chris Kellogg [7] in their study propose a novel framework that leverages the physical properties for mining data scarce domains. The method introduced interleaves bottom-up data mining with top-down data collection leading to effective and explainable sampling strategies. They thus explore the active learning aspect of data mining to inherit some of the principles of Bayesian inductive inference for efficient data classification in the spatial domain.

4. DATA CLEANING, CLUSTERING AND CLASSIFICATION:

Data cleaning was done as an apriori step to the final data clustering and classification using supervised learning and unsupervised learning. These include feature selection, feature extraction and error analysis through error contour plots and error surface analysis. This was restricted to visualizing the magnitude of the mean square error (MSE) and sum of squared error

(SSE) resulting from the aforementioned exercises. The purposes of data cleaning were:

- elimination of noise
- relevant-irrelevant feature identification
- precise class labeling
- sample selection
- randomizing data and biases
- LS error minimization (MSE, SSE)

4.1 Supervised Learning:

Data cleaning through supervised learning involved feature/sample selection using the decision tree learning including split evaluation function (SEF), information gain (IG), negative gain ratio (NGR) and entropy (EN) parameters. The digitized image data set was introduced to a Matlab program that devised the right node to split on based on the SEF, IG, NGR and EN values being in excess of or below a specified threshold value,. All sample sets that satisfied these criteria were deemed relevant and the others filtered out. The illustration of this exercise is seen below. Most decision tree algorithms continue to split until no further splits are possible. Both the attribute to split and the location of the split along that attribute are chosen to minimize the split evaluation function, SEF, given by $SEF = (|t_L| / |t|) * I(t_L) + |t_R| / |t| * I(t_R)$ where t_L and t_R = the left and right splits, t = number of training instances, I = corresponding impurity function given by $I(t) = I(p_1, \dots, p_c)$ where p_1, \dots, p_c are the class probability vectors given by $p_i = N_i/N$ and $N = N_1 + N_2 + \dots + N_c$

fig1: the plot of the SEF (optimal node x = 24.9)

To produce the smallest tree it is natural to choose the split that brings about the greatest increase in “purity” at each step. Three measures of impurity that have been used in this exercise are – *Inaccuracy* defined by $I(p_1, \dots, p_c) = 1 - \max_i p_i$,

fig2: the plot of the IN

Entropy defined by $E(p_1, \dots, p_c) = - \sum_{i=1}^c p_i \log(p_i)$, $i = 1$ to c

fig3: the plot of the EN

and *Negative gain ratio* defined by $NGR(p_1, \dots, p_c) = 1 - S - p_i^2$, $i = 1$ to c

fig4: the plot of the NGR

The accuracy of the above exercise was intrinsically evaluated using the *bootstrapping* algorithm. In recent years the statistical literature has examined the properties of re-sampling as a means to acquire information about the uncertainty of statistical estimators. The bootstrap is a procedure that involves choosing random samples with replacement from a data set and analyzing each sample the same way. Sampling with replacement means that every sample is returned to the data set after sampling. The number

of elements in each bootstrap sample equals the number of elements in the original data set. The range of sample estimates we obtain allows us to establish the uncertainty of the quantity we are estimating. From rho-hat (cross-correlation) values, we have a number, 0.4367, describing the positive connection between corn and soybean, but though 0.4367 may seem large, we still do not know if it is statistically significant. The sigma (co-variance) values are of the order of 10^4 suggesting high inter-dependence and correlation in the data set. From the histogram, nearly all the estimates lie on the interval [0.1 0.7] and [-0.2 0.3]. The former indicates strong quantitative evidence that corn and subsequent soybean are positively correlated.

fig5: the linear db plot between classes corn and waterbody

fig6: the histogram plot of the correlation coeff between the chosen classes – corn and waterbody

With the feature selection now complete feature extraction was carried out on the sample/feature set that was now partially cleaned and carefully handpicked. This was done using the *hierarchical clustering* algorithm. Hierarchical clustering is a way to investigate grouping in the data, simultaneously over a variety of scales, by creating a cluster tree. The tree is not a single set of clusters, but rather a multi-level hierarchy, where clusters at one level are joined as clusters at the next higher level. This allows the user to decide what level or scale of clustering is most appropriate in the application. To perform hierarchical cluster analysis on a data set follow this procedure:

Find the similarity or dissimilarity between every pair of objects in the data set. In this step, calculate the distance between objects using a distance function. The function supports many different metrics to compute this measurement. Group the objects into a binary, hierarchical cluster tree. In this step, link together pairs of objects that are in close proximity using some linkage function. The linkage function uses the distance information generated in step 1 to determine the proximity of objects to each other. As objects are paired into binary clusters, the newly formed clusters are grouped into larger clusters until a hierarchical tree is formed. Determine where to divide the hierarchical tree into clusters. In this step, divide the objects in the hierarchical tree into clusters using the cluster function. The cluster function can create clusters by detecting natural groupings in the hierarchical tree or by cutting off the hierarchical tree at an arbitrary point. $h = 3$ in the output matrix indicates the optimal tree size for the node split for the chosen parameter, corn. $c = 0.9278$ is the correlation coefficient which compares the distance information, and the distance information in Y, generated by the chosen distance metric. The above value suggests a huge cross-correlation between the selected variables, corn and wheat.

fig7: the silhouette plot of the clusters

fig8: the dendrogram plot of the binary clusters

Now with a set of clean data under uniform and precise class and cost variations data clustering was carried out using the *regression and classification tree* algorithm. In nonlinear least squares it is supposed

that the user knows the form of the relationship between the response and predictor. Suppose instead that the user does not know that relationship and also that he is unwilling to assume the relationship, then it can be well approximated by a linear model. Hence, the user needs a more nonparametric type of regression fitting approach. One such approach is based on "trees." A *regression tree* is a sequence of questions that can be answered as yes or no, plus a set of fitted response values. Each question asks whether a predictor satisfies a given condition. Predictors can be continuous or discrete. Depending on the answers to one question, the user either proceeds to another question or arrives at a fitted response value. First, load the data and then create a matrix x of predictor values and a vector y of response variables. Continue moving down the tree until arriving at a terminal node that gives the predicted value. The best tree is the one that has a residual variance that is no more than one standard error above the minimum value along the cross-validation line. In this case the variance is just over 7. With a tree like this one having many branches, there is a danger that it fits the current data set well but would not do a good job at predicting new values. Some of its lower branches may be strongly affected by outliers and other artifacts of the current data set. If possible it would be preferable to find a simpler tree that avoids this problem of over-fitting. Estimate the best tree size by cross validation. First, compute a "re-substitution" estimate of the error variance for this tree and a sequence of simpler trees and plot it as the lower (blue) line in the figure. This estimate probably under-estimates the true error variance. Then compute a "cross-validation" estimate of the same quantity and plot it as the upper (red) line. The cross-validation procedure also provides us with an estimate of the pruning level, "best", needed to achieve the best tree size.

fig9: the optimal TD tree search

fig10: the plot of the best tree estimate

The final data classification was done using the Bayesian classifier algorithm. In this method, also known as the Bayes' hypothesis testing procedure, the average risk is minimized to yield the optimal linear classification boundary. Assuming an 8-class Gaussian distributed problem the following equations hold: $Y = W^T X + b$ where $Y = \text{linear classifier} = \log P(X)$ for $X = \text{the source or the input data vector}$, $W = \text{the weight vector} = C^{-1}(\mu_1 - \mu_2, \dots)$, $B = \text{the bias vector} = \frac{1}{2}(\mu_2^T C^{-1} \mu_2 - \mu_1^T C^{-1} \mu_1, \dots)$ for a covariance matrix $C = E[(X - \mu)(X - \mu)^T]$

fig11: the final classification plot of the chosen classes: corn and road ways

4.2 Unsupervised Learning:

Data cleaning through unsupervised learning involved feature/sample selection, feature extraction and data clustering using the k-means algorithm with EM in combination with the Bayesian classifier. This algorithm moves objects between clusters until the sum cannot be decreased further. The result is a set of clusters that are as compact and well-separated as possible. One can control the details of the minimization using several optional input parameters to k-means, including ones for the initial values of the cluster centroids, and for the maximum number of iterations. $Q(h'/h) = S \ln \frac{1}{(2ps^2)^{1/2}} - \frac{1}{2} s^2 S [z_{ij}^2 (x_i - \mu_j')^2]$ for $i = 1$ to m and $j = 1$ to k where $m = \text{total number of instances of data}$, $k = \text{total number of normal distributions}$, $\mu = \text{vector of means}$, $s = \text{vector of standard deviations}$, $s^2 = \text{covariance matrix}$, $z = \text{total number of hidden variables}$, $x = \text{input data}$, $h =$

current hypothesis, h' = given hypothesis, Q = function defined for the EM process.

Step 1: Estimation step

$$Q(h'/h) = E[\ln P(Y/h') | h, X] \text{ for } Y = X \text{ ? } Z$$

where \cup = union operator indicating the full data set.

Step 2: Maximization step

$$h' = \operatorname{argmax}_h Q(h'/h) \text{ given } h'$$

so as to estimate the parameters, $\theta = \langle \mu_1 \mu_2 \dots \dots \dots \mu_k \rangle$ that define the k normal distributions.

From the silhouette plot, it can be seen that most points in the third cluster have a large silhouette value, greater than 0.6, indicating that that cluster is somewhat separated from neighboring clusters. However, the second cluster contains many points with low silhouette values, and the first contains a few points with negative values, indicating that those two clusters are not well separated.

fig12: the silhouette plot of the clusters from EM

The final Bayesian classifier output after the unsupervised learning is given below for the same set of data classes as the supervised learning.

fig13: the final classification plot of the chosen classes: corn and road ways

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

The data obtained was a multi-spectral ERDAS RGB color coded remote sensing image of an agricultural land mass in north central Indiana. The data was recorded and archived as flight line FIC1.lan in BIL format. Experimenting with the data set using the aforementioned and enlisted machine learning and

data mining exercises and MultiSpec software yielded the following results that were comparable in some aspects while statistically differing significantly in various other aspects.

5.1 Supervised vs. Unsupervised Learning:

Both the learning methods were backed by using a detailed statistical significance analysis quantified by PCA, ICA and FA. It was observed that the error analysis and the statistical analysis yielded very comparable results between the two. But on closer inspection from an end classification point of view it was seen that data cleaning was better in supervised learning in terms of elimination of noise, class labeling, sample selection, randomizing data and biases and LS error minimization (MSE, SSE). The following illustrations indicate similar performances in terms of residual and error magnitudes, biases, PCA, ICA and FA by both the learning techniques.

fig14: the error surface/contour plot

fig15: the plot of the residuals of classification

The T^2 statistics vector is all positive and takes every value > 1 , indicating that the null hypothesis proposed is validated. The residuals obtained during the process are all < 1 excepting for one data parameter that is slightly > 1 indicating a very accurate linear least squares fit. Looking at the plot we can notice that corn and soybean essentially bias the data set mainly because of a greater number of data samples respectively.

fig16: the plot of the LS best fit line between projected data points of corn and wheat

fig19: the ICA signal histogram plot for corn

fig17: the plot of % variability from PCA

The plot used in this context would be to see how well the separated ICA-signals explain the observed mixed signals.

fig18: the ICA mixture signal plot for all 8 clusters

From the estimated specific variances, we can see that the model indicates that a particular corn data point varies quite a lot beyond the variation due to the common factors. A specific variance of 1 would indicate that there is no common factor component in that variable; while a specific variance of 0 would indicate that the variable is entirely determined by common factors. These data seem to fall somewhere in between.

Based on which clusters are near which axes, the user could reasonably conclude that the first factor axis represents the wheat, the second soybean and the third to a relatively low extent red clover. The original conjecture that corn varies primarily within sector is apparently supported by the data. The lambda matrix contains the maximum log-likelihood parameter values. On inspection it is noticed that these values range from -0.0422 for wasteland cluster to 0.9757 for the cluster, corn. Finally the loglike parameters denotes the maximized log-likelihood value for the chosen parameter corn, indicating how well the data set pertaining to that particular variable can be efficiently classified with respect to all other parameters using a linear decision boundary. A low value indicates superior performance on the end classification. The error degrees of freedom are explained by the dfe parameter and a low value suggests higher classification accuracy. On inspection it is seen that $dfe = 13$ and $loglike = -1.3660$ indicating precise classification due to a reduced error matrix and hence minimal residual values.

fig20: the correlation plot from FA between the chosen classes: corn, soybean and wheat

5.2 Machine Learning vs. MultiSpec

On using the MultiSpec software obtained training accuracy was of the order of **86.4%** while the predetermined test accuracy was in the range of **75-85%** for the end classification statistic. In this procedure the conventional pattern recognition methods including feature selection using mean

Bhattacharya distance metric, decision boundary feature extraction, ISODATA statistical clustering with Bayesian classification were used. With the error surface command an error matrix that was in the range of approximately 10^{-15} was obtained while the sum of squared error, SSE, turned out to be $3.3157 * 10^{-29}$. From the decision tree program the value of the negative gain ratio obtained was **0.081081**, that of entropy was **0.054054** and finally the inaccuracy was found to be **0.148649** reflecting a feature selection accuracy of approximately **85.14%**. These results were found for 6, 4 & 11 nodes respectively and 74 leaves each. These values were small indicating optimal performance with acceptable results. From the Bayesian classifier algorithm under ML domain, it can be concluded that the residuals were very close to **0** and the training class accuracy was approximately **97.22%** with the algorithm converging after **4** iterations thereby avoiding local minima.

Table 1: Comparison of Accuracies

Method	Algorithms	Training class accuracy
MultiSpec	Bhatta dist FS, dbFE, isodata, Bayes	~ 86.40%
Unsup Learning	K-means and Bayes	
Sup Learning	Dec Trees, bootstrapping, Bayes	~ 97.22%
NN	Backprop, AVQ, SOM, LVQ etc	~ 98.02%

6. CONCLUSIONS:

The conclusions and inferences that can be drawn from the study include—learning algorithm based machine learning and data mining techniques displayed on an average, better results in terms of accuracy as these procedures work on the principle of error minimization. The second advantage with these procedures was the minimization of biases by randomizing the data. All ML/KD/DM algorithms helped capture non-linearity to a greater extent and most end results after simulation plotted linear classified data points. Scaling, over-fitting the data, temporal changes in the variables, occurrence of local minima and other such algorithm related problems did not surface when using the data mining methods indicating superior adaptivity, greater robust nature of the programs and hence more accurate learning. Finally, the ML/DM accounted for, comparatively much better, when it came to modeling noisy data and data irregularities. MultiSpec software with classical pattern recognition tools performed well with linear data that was not correlated and was normally distributed. This may well be stated as a limitation of the software. Also randomizing the data was not possible. However, the program would be ideal when performing dimensionality reduction and other such exercises. Also, it provides menu-driven user-friendly techniques to perform FE, clustering, PCA, FS apart

from having a great advantage of being able to produce quality end classification maps that are helpful for the purposes of presentation and facilitate easy understanding and interpretation.

7. FUTURE WORK:

It is proposed to extend this study by trying to quantify error at each stage and hence establish which ML techniques perform significantly and which don't. Further, it is planned to extend this research to the analysis of hyper-spectral, thermal, IR, RADAR and LIDAR imagery so as to achieve maximum and optimal data classification and information extraction. Also, a query based spatial data base development using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology, integrating with Global Positioning Systems (GPS) method to determine the Z-dimension and statistical modeling and analysis would be interesting follows on the project. It is planned to combine all these techniques through a selective approach that uses the best of all methods along with experimenting with Support Vector Machines (SVM). In conclusion, archiving the results obtained from using MultiSpec, neural networks, fuzzy logic systems, neural fuzzy systems and machine learning & data mining techniques on the same data set is possible. Testing the relevance and applicability of other useful methods from the areas of digital image processing, genetic algorithms and scientific data visualization for analysis is noteworthy and warrants research attention.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

- [1] *Simon Haykin* -- Neural Networks: A Comprehensive Foundation, II edition, Pearson Education Asia, 1999
- [2] *Craig W. Codrington* -- Decision Trees
- [3] Classification of Spatial Data by Decision Tree Induction using Peano Count Tree -- *Amalendu Roy* @ www.cs.ndsu.nodak.edu
- [4] Data Farming Methods for Temporal Data Mining -- *Andrew Kusiak* @ www.icaen.uiowa.edu
- [5] On Mining Satellite and other Remotely Sensed Images -- *William Perrizo, Qin Ding, Qiang Din* and *Amalendu Roy* @ www.cs.ndsu.nodak.edu
- [6] Spatial Data Mining on RSI - A Case Study
- [7] Sampling Strategies for Mining in Data -- Scarce Domains -- *Naren Ramakrishnan* and *Chris Bailey-Kellogg*, IEEE 2002
- [8] *Thomas M. Lillesand* and *Ralph W. Kiefer* -- Remote Sensing and Image Interpretation: IV edition, John Wiley & Sons Inc, 2000
- [9] *Tom Mitchell* -- Machine Learning, International Edition, McGraw-Hill, 1997
- [10] *Hyvärinen, Karhunen* and *Oja* -- Independent Component Analysis, John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- [11] Data Source: <http://dynamo.ecn.purdue.edu/~biehl/MultiSpec/documentation.html>
- [12] *Chin-Teng Lin* & *C.S. George Lee* -- Neural Fuzzy Systems: A Neuro-Fuzzy Synergism to Intelligent Systems, Prentice Hall, 1996